

Two mitochondrial phosphatases, PP2c63 and Sal2, are required for posttranslational regulation of the TCA cycle in Arabidopsis

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ABSTRACT

Protein phosphorylation is a well-established post-translational mechanism that regulates protein functions and metabolic pathways. It is known that several plant mitochondrial proteins are phosphorylated in a reversible manner. However, the identities of the protein kinases/phosphatases involved in this mechanism and their roles in the regulation of the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle remain unclear. In this study, we isolated and characterized plants lacking two mitochondrially targeted phosphatases (Sal2 and PP2c63) along with pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase (PDK). Protein-protein interaction analysis, quantitative phosphoproteomics, and enzymatic analyses revealed that PDK specifically regulates pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDC), while PP2c63 nonspecifically regulates PDC. When recombinant PP2c63 and Sal2 proteins were added to mitochondria isolated from mutant plants, protein-protein interaction and enzymatic analyses showed that PP2c63 directly phosphorylates and modulates the activity of PDC, while Sal2 only indirectly affects TCA cycle enzymes. Characterization of steady-state metabolite levels and fluxes in the mutant lines further revealed that these phosphatases regulate flux through the TCA cycle, and that altered metabolism in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant compromises plant growth. These results are discussed in the context of current models of the control of respiration in plants.

Key words: TCA cycle, pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphorylation, mitochondrial protein phosphatase, TCA cycle enzymes phosphorylation

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INTRODUCTION

Although considerable knowledge concerning the *in vivo* function of enzymes of the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle in plants has been amassed (Fernie et al., 2004, 2018; Araújo et al., 2011b; Centeno et al., 2011; Araujo et al., 2012; Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013), our understanding of the regulation of this important pathway is still fragmentary (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013). A previous metabolic analysis showed that much of the control in the TCA cycle resides in fumarase, malate dehydrogenase (MDH), and oxoglutarate dehydrogenase (OGDH) (Araujo et al., 2012), suggesting that these enzymes could be sensitive

targets for flux regulation. However, in contrast to plastid-based pathways (Stitt et al., 2010), the lack of resolution in subcellular analysis of TCA cycle intermediates in mitochondria currently precludes the use of disequilibrium ratios to assess the potential of enzymes to play regulatory roles in this pathway. That said, there is a growing body of information concerning allosteric and post-translational modifications of the constituent enzymes (Araujo et al., 2012;

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Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013; Tripodi et al., 2015). Such information is provided both by (1) traditional studies on enzyme effectors (Thomas and Fell, 1998; Zhang and Fernie, 2018), and (2) more recent broad-based studies of changes in transcript abundance, protein abundance, post-translational modifications of proteins, and overall metabolite levels in response to experimental perturbations (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013; Fernie et al., 2018; Zhang and Fernie, 2018; Møller et al., 2020). Post-translational modifications include not only phosphorylation but also, for example, acetylation (Fernie et al., 2004; König et al., 2014; LaPorte and Koshland, 1982; Møller et al., 2020).

Much of the research on the TCA cycle in plants has focused on the reaction catalyzed by the pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDC) – which although not strictly a part of the TCA cycle is intimately associated with it (Fernie et al., 2004; Lan et al., 2012; Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013; Ohbayashi et al., 2019). The PDC consists of three components: pyruvate dehydrogenase (E1), dihydrolipoyl acetyltransferase (E2), and dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase (E3) (Fernie et al., 2004; Lan et al., 2012; Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013; Ohbayashi et al., 2019; Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003). There are two distinct PDCs in plant cells – one in mitochondria, which is the entry point to the TCA cycle, and one in the plastid, which provides acetyl-CoA and NADH for de novo fatty acid biosynthesis (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003). The mitochondrial PDC has two associated regulatory enzymes: pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase (PDK) and phospho-pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase (PDP), although the gene encoding the latter has yet to be identified (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003). *In vitro* studies suggest exquisite regulation of the PDC, which balances its phosphorylation status with its complex metabolite-mediated regulation, with pyruvate and thiamine pyrophosphate acting as positive effectors (Bocobza et al., 2013; Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003), and NADH, acetyl-CoA, ammonium, and glyoxylate as inhibitors (Plaxton and Podestá, 2006). However, the relative contributions of phosphorylation and the various metabolite effectors to PDC regulation have not been clarified. For example, elegant studies from the Møller laboratory have indicated that the free NADH concentration of plant mitochondria is maintained at constant levels across many conditions, rendering it important to interpret implications of *in vitro* kinetics with caution (Kasimova et al., 2006). Indeed, downregulation of the inhibitory PDK in Arabidopsis resulted in plants displaying altered vegetative growth, early flower development, and shorter generation time (Zou et al., 1999), whereas a mutation in the E2 subunit that should confer an opposite effect on PDC activity resulted in a similar phenotype (Yu et al., 2012). Such observations indicate that plant growth depends not only on total PDC activity, but also on its correct regulation.

Beyond the PDC, a range of allosteric (for a full list see Bocobza et al., 2013) and other regulatory properties have been described or suggested on the basis of proteomic studies for enzymes of the TCA cycle. These include the identification of potential phosphorylation and redox regulation sites within citrate synthase, aconitase, isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH), OGDH, succinyl CoA ligase (SCoAL), succinate dehydrogenase (SDH), fumarase, and MDH, as well as an acetylation site within MDH (Bykova et al., 2003a, 2003b; Havelund et al., 2013; König et al., 2014; Schmidtman et al., 2014). Aconitase is highly

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sensitive to oxidative stress and NO (Moeder et al., 2007), OGDH and SCoAL are subject to light-dependent regulation (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013), and SDH is sensitive to phytochrome and NO regulation (Affourtit et al., 2001; Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013). Transcripts encoding enzymes of the TCA cycle are highly induced following osmotic, salt, and UV-B stress, while at the protein level, there is a decrease in fumarase and accumulation of MDH under oxidative stress (Tomaz et al., 2010; Araujo et al., 2012), and an increase in aconitase, IDH, 2-oxoglutarate dehydrogenase (E2 subunit), and MDH in response to flooding (Lehmann et al., 2009, 2012; Dumont and Rivoal, 2019). Coordinate redox control was demonstrated in a recent study of the role of thioredoxin $\alpha 1$ in the control of the Arabidopsis TCA cycle (Daloso et al., 2015). This study revealed that, via its action on SDH and fumarase, thioredoxin effectively modulates flux through the pathway.

A large number of potential phosphorylation sites in enzymes of the TCA cycle are listed in the PhosPhAt database (Zulawski et al., 2012). This prompted us to perform a systematic investigation of the possible role of phosphorylation in the regulation of this pathway. For this purpose, we investigated candidate proteins that had been isolated with medium confidence in previous TCA cycle interactome studies (Zhang et al., 2017, 2018). We analyzed knockout mutants in *pp2c63* (protein phosphatase 2C 63) and *Sal2* (SIT4 phosphatase-associated protein) and, for comparison, a *pdk* knockout line with respect to their phosphoproteomes, the overall activity and kinetic characteristics of selected enzymes, metabolite levels, labeling patterns, and whole plant phenotypes. Loss of either of the two phosphatases or the lack of PDK had effects on phosphorylation patterns, enzyme activities, and the levels of metabolites associated with the TCA cycle. Our results suggest that both PP2c63 and Sal2 regulate the *in vivo* activity of pyruvate dehydrogenase and that they work in an additive manner. These results are discussed in the context of current models of the regulation of the plant TCA cycle.

RESULTS

Mitochondrial phosphatases and the PDK kinase are important for plant growth

Earlier affinity-purification mass spectrometry (AP-MS) studies indicated that both Sal2 and PP2c63 interact weakly with TCA cycle enzymes (Zhang et al., 2017, 2018). To further investigate the potential roles of PP2c63, Sal2, and the previously reported PDK (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2005) in regulating the mitochondrial TCA cycle, we isolated two independent T-DNA insertion mutants each for gene: *pp2c63* (AT4g33920, SALK_143298 and GABI_494G12), *sal2* (AT1g30470, SAIL_142_C10 and SALK_122002), and *pdk* (AT3G06483, SALK_018663 and SALK_014790) (Supplemental Figure 1A and 1B). In addition, we generated double and triple mutant lines.

Growth was not altered in single mutants but was strongly decreased in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (Figure 1A and Supplemental Figure 1C–1E). This growth phenotype could be partially complemented by the native PP2c63 fused to a C-terminal GFP. Given the great difficulty of transforming this

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Figure 1. The mitochondrially localized Sal2, PP2c63, and PDK regulate plant growth and development.

(A) Plant growth phenotype under short-day conditions at 30 days. (B) Number of leaves of 30-day old plants. (C) Fresh weight of 30-day old plants. The subcellular localization of Sal2 (D), PP2c63 (E), and PDK (F) was analyzed by transforming WT Arabidopsis plants with constructs carrying a genomic sequence including the native promoter and a translational GFP fusion. Mts-mCherry is the mitochondria targeted mCherry. WT, wild type; Sal2, SIT4 phosphatase-associated protein; PP2c63, protein phosphatase 2C 63; PDK, Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase.

that coincided with localization of mCherry containing a mitochondrial targeting peptide (Figure 1D–1F).

Both the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant and *sal2 pp2c63 pdk* triple mutant had a lower chlorophyll content than WT. Nevertheless, all mutants showed unaltered rates of carbon assimilation (Supplemental Figure 2). Furthermore, several chlorophyll a fluorescence parameters (linear electron flux, the redox state of the PSII acceptor side [qL], and non-photochemical quenching [qN]) were unchanged in all the single, double, and triple mutant plants (Supplemental Figure 2C–2E).

Quantitative phosphoproteomics of the *sal2*, *pp2c63*, and *pdk* mutants

Despite being one of the most well characterized post-translational modifications, phosphorylation of plant mitochondrial proteins remains poorly explored (Finkemeier and Schwarzländer, 2018; Havelund et al., 2013; Möller, 2016). To date, only phosphorylation of pyruvate dehydrogenase (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003) and formate dehydrogenase (Bykova et al., 2003a, 2003b) have

been characterized in detail. Here we analyzed the phosphoproteomic changes resulting from PDK inactivation as well as the loss of two phosphatases, Sal2 and PP2c63. Given that the process of mitochondrial isolation could affect the phosphorylation status of proteins, we used total cellular protein extracts from 30-day-old Arabidopsis plants harvested at midday for phosphoproteomic analyses, as well as for quantification of protein abundances. In total, more than 6,500 protein groups containing 11,000 phosphosites were quantified from four biological replicates of four mutant lines and WT plants (Supplemental Table 1 and Supplemental Figures 3–8). Of the quantified phosphosites, nearly 300 belonged to mitochondrial proteins according to the subcellular localization prediction software SUBA4 (Hooper et al., 2017) (Supplemental Figure 5, Supplemental Table 1). Hundreds of significant phosphosite changes in proteins from other subcellular compartments were

sickly mutant, only one line was produced. In addition, the fully complemented *sal2-3* and *pp2c63* mutants expressing Sal2 and PP2c63 under their native promoters (Psal2: *sal2* and Pp2c63: *pp2c63*, respectively) were crossed with *sal2-3 pp2c63-1* and characterization of the progeny revealed that the plant growth phenotype could be fully complemented in the double mutant background (Supplemental Figure 1). After growth in standard short-day conditions (8 h light/16 h dark), shoot material was subsequently harvested from 30-day-old plants, and the fresh weight (FW) was determined at harvest. Relative to wild type (WT), a significant reduction in FW was observed for the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (Figure 1B and 1C). The sub-cellular localization of both phosphatases and PDK was confirmed by transient expression of the C-terminal GFP-tagged proteins with the mitochondrial mCherry marker (Zhang et al., 2020a). They exhibited a punctate distribution

Name	Identifier	Phosphopeptides	Loc.	Score	Delta score	<i>pdk</i>	<i>sal2</i>	<i>pp2c63</i>	<i>sal2 pp2c63</i>
			Prob.						
mMDH1	AT1G53240	SFS(0.988)S(0.012) GSVPER	0.99	133.4	116.5	-0.63 ^{0.37}	0.12 ^{0.62}	1.04 ^{0.00}	0.93 ^{0.02}
FUM1/FUM2	AT2G47510 AT5G50950	S(1)FEFKDIVK	1.00	85.81	59.8	0.07 ^{0.94}	1.80 ^{0.15}	-1.93 ^{0.04}	-0.45 ^{0.52}
PDC1a-1/ PDC1a-2	AT1G24180 AT1G59900	YHGHS(1)MSDPGSTYR	1.00	224.2	205.4	-8.80 ^{0.00}	-0.52 ^{0.38}	-1.35 ^{0.09}	-0.09 ^{0.71}
PDC1a-1/ PDC1a-2	AT1G24180 AT1G59900	YHGHSMS(0.929) DPGSTYR	0.93	109.8	79.8	-2.26 ^{0.06}	-0.89 ^{0.28}	1.75 ^{0.02}	2.65 ^{0.00}

Table 1. Quantification of the identified phosphosites of the TCA cycle enzymes mMDH1, fumarase, and PDC1a in the mitochondrial kinase (*pdk*) and phosphatase (*sal2*, *pp2c63*, and *sal2 pp2c63*) mutants compared with WT in midday samples (n = 4)

Average and log₂-transformed ratios relative to the WT are reported. Student's t test *P* values are given in superscripts. In the case of PDC1a, two isoforms share the same phosphopeptide. Phosphosite (P-site) positions within the protein are given. Maxquant localization probabilities (Loc.Prob.) as an indicator of correct phosphosite identification, as well as peptide scores and delta scores, are provided in brackets. The full list of quantified phosphosites and protein groups can be found in [Supplemental Table 1](#). Significant changes (*P* < 0.05) are highlighted by bold font.

also found in the mutants compared with WT ([Supplemental Figure 5](#) and [Supplemental Table 1A](#)). This can be explained by an indirect effect of mitochondrial dysfunction on signaling and metabolism elsewhere in the cell.

Significant changes in the abundance of phosphosites were also detected for PDC and some TCA cycle enzymes ([Table 1](#) and [Supplemental Table 1](#), and [Supplemental Figure 6](#)). As expected, the abundances of two phosphosites of the two mitochondrial isoforms of the E1 alpha subunit of pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDC1a) were strongly reduced in the *pdk* mutant ([Table 1](#)). Phosphorylation occupancy calculations revealed that approximately 90% of PDC1a-1 was phosphorylated in WT plants at midday and that phosphorylation was nearly completely lost in the *pdk* mutant (0.03%) ([Supplemental Figure 7](#)). PDC1a is encoded by two genes, which share 100% sequence homology in the detected phosphopeptide (YHGHSMSDPGSTYR) and carry up to two phosphorylated serines (S292 and S294 in case of AT1G59900, and S296 and S298 in case of AT1G24180). Both sites have been previously reported in several studies ([Willems et al., 2019](#)). Mutation of the first serine residue (S296 in AT1G24180) to Asp, mimics inactivation and constant phosphorylation of the protein, which results in a dwarf phenotype ([Lan et al., 2012](#)). The data from Lan and coworkers (2012) indicate that S292/296 controls PDC activity, while the contribution of S294/S298 remains unclear. It should be noted that PDC is fully inactivated by phosphorylation in the light, and is then dynamically dephosphorylated upon darkness ([Budde and Randall, 1990](#)). Changes in phosphorylation status during the day/night cycle add an additional layer of complexity when comparing phosphosite abundance in the mutants analyzed. Therefore, while phosphorylation of PDC can be best monitored in WT plants in the light, PDC activity can be best monitored in the dark or during the onset of light. There was no phosphorylation difference in S292/S296 between WT and the phosphatase mutants in samples harvested at midday, due to complete phosphorylation of this site in WT plants. However, a difference between mutant lines and WT was observed at S294/S298 sites, only a few percent of which were phosphorylated in the light ([Supplemental Table 1](#)). Interestingly in the *pp2c63* single

mutant, an increase in the abundance (3-fold) of the phosphosite S294/S298 on a single phosphorylated peptide was observed. This effect was even more pronounced in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (6-fold), indicating that PP2C63 and Sal2 cooperate in the dephosphorylation of PDC1a ([Table 1](#)). Interestingly, no increase in S294/S298 phosphorylation was detected for PDC1a in the single *sal2* mutant, which may indicate that PP2C63 overcompensates in the absence of Sal2. In addition, the double phosphorylated peptide was only detected once in the *sal2 pp2c63* mutant and so could not be quantified further. Therefore, it appears that PDC1a exists in different proteoforms, which might involve sequential (de)-phosphorylation of both serines. The unmodified peptide could not be detected in the *pp2c63* and *sal2 pp2c63* mutants. This prevented the calculation of phosphosite occupancies in these mutants and indicates that PDC1a is almost completely phosphorylated in mutants and WT as expected for midday samples.

Since PDC phosphorylation changes during the day/night cycle, we additionally performed a targeted proteomic analysis using parallel reaction monitoring (PRM) next to the standard label free quantification analyses of PDC phosphopeptides in samples harvested at the onset of the light ([Supplemental Table 1C](#) and [1D](#) and [Supplemental Figure 8](#)). Under these conditions, only 10% to 50% of the PDC1a-1 protein was phosphorylated at S292/S296 in WT plants. At this time of day, S294/S298 phosphorylation was not yet detectable. Therefore, under these early morning conditions, where we expected the mitochondrial phosphatases in WT to be active and where PDK would become gradually activated, we observed a significantly higher proportion of phosphorylated S292/S296 residue in the *sal2* mutant as well as in the *pp2c63* mutant ([Supplemental Figure 8](#)). This effect was also observed in the double mutant, which had higher average phosphorylation levels. However, as this effect was only clearly visible in two of the four biological replicates of the double mutant, this value shows a rather large SD.

Next to PDC1a, both *pp2c63* and *sal2 pp2c63* mutants showed a significant increase in the abundance of phosphosite S23, by approximately 2-fold, in the MDH isoform mMDH1

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(AT1G53240.1) (Table 1). Phosphorylation of S23 in mMDH1 was independent of PDK, as no significant change was observed for this site in the *pdk* mutant. The phosphosite S23 of mMDH1 has also been observed in other proteomic studies (Willems et al., 2019).

In addition, the phosphosite S203/S210 can be assigned to both fumarase 1 and 2 (AT2G47510, AT5G50950), and is derived from a mis-cleaved peptide. This phosphosite has also been previously detected in other large-scale proteomic studies (Mergner et al., 2020). Here, loss of Sal2 led to an increase in abundance of this phosphosite (Table 1 and Supplemental Table 1). Interestingly, the loss of PP2c63 had a negative effect on the phosphorylation level of fumarase and a similar, though smaller decrease, was observed in the *sal2 pp2c63* mutant. This negative effect may be due to secondary effects in the *pp2c63* mutant. For example, reduced fumarase kinase activity or overcompensation by another phosphatase may produce such a result. Such compensatory effects have been previously observed in other phosphatase mutants (Xiang et al., 2016).

In summary, phosphoproteomics data indicate that both Sal2 and PP2c63 are important for the regulation of phosphorylation status of PDC1. Although this dataset is rather extensive, it is important to remember that other phosphosites may exist that could be regulated by the same enzymes, but are not detectable using proteomic approaches relying on the trypsination of proteins. Thus, further studies are required to elucidate the target proteins of these phosphatases in mitochondria.

Disruption of *Sal2*, *PP2c63*, and *PDK* alters the activity of TCA cycle enzymes

We further investigated the overall activity and kinetic characteristics of PDC, fumarase, and MDH (Figure 2, Supplemental Figures 9 and 10). In order to ascertain whether the phosphostatus of proteins had an effect on enzyme activity assays, four substrate concentrations, including non-saturating conditions, were used for all enzymes. Activity changes under limiting versus saturating substrate conditions could point to a post-translational modification that alters substrate affinity, while parallel changes in activity under limiting and saturating substrate conditions may indicate either post-translational regulation of the enzyme, or a change in protein abundance (with data on the latter being required to distinguish the two scenarios). To address possible complications due to non-mitochondrial isoforms, one set of analyses was performed on extracts of mitochondria isolated from 20-day-old plants harvested in the middle of the day. In the analyses with mitochondrial extracts, the K_m of PDC was slightly lower in *pdk* mutant lines, and higher in the *pp2c63* and *sal2 pp2c63* mutant lines compared with WT (Figure 2A and 2C). The K_m of PDC was unchanged in the *sal2* mutant. The K_m of fumarase was higher in the *pp2c63* and *sal2 pp2c63* mutant lines (Supplemental Figure 9A and 9C), while it was unaltered in the other lines.

Using whole leaf extracts, we investigated the K_m of both PDC and fumarase at six time points during a diel cycle. In WT plants, analysis of the enzyme kinetics of total cellular PDC revealed a lower K_m and V_{max} in the light (Supplemental Figure 11A), which is similar to results presented for isolated mitochondria in a

previous study (Lee et al., 2010). Diurnal changes in K_m and V_{max} of both PDC and fumarase were altered in the *sal2* and *sal2 pp2c63* mutants, indicating a possible indirect regulatory function of Sal2 in controlling TCA cycle flux. This finding was also consistent with both lower starch accumulation and degradation in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant during the day and night, respectively.

MDH enzyme activity was increased under saturating substrate conditions but not under limiting conditions in the *sal2* and *pp2c63* single mutants and in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (Supplemental Table 2 and Supplemental Figure 10). These findings were the same irrespective of whether the measurement was made using total cellular extracts or extracts from isolated mitochondria (Supplemental Figure 10). Activities of several other TCA cycle enzymes were measured in total protein extracts. Aconitase activity under saturated substrate conditions was increased in *sal2 pp2c63* (Supplemental Table 2). NADP⁺-isocitrate dehydrogenase activity was also significantly increased in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (Supplemental Table 2); however, phosphopeptides from this enzyme were not detected. In summary, these data match the expectation that PDK regulates pyruvate dehydrogenase, and also indicate that PP2c63 may regulate fumarase.

To provide further evidence that these phosphatases regulate TCA cycle enzymes, mitochondria were purified from the *pp2c63* lines. As we did not obtain sufficient seeds to grow enough plants to allow for mitochondrial purification from the *sal2 pp2c63* mutant (which also had a dwarf phenotype), recombinant PP2c63 and Sal2 were purified from plant cell cultures. Using the lambda PPase (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA) and NEBuffer Pack for Protein MetalloPhosphatase buffer, standard phosphorylation conditions were set up for testing PDC activity. Total mitochondrial proteins from *pp2c63* cells were treated with a mock treatment, PP2c63, Sal2, or Sal2+PP2c63 under standard dephosphorylation conditions for 30 min. In addition, total mitochondrial proteins from *sal2* were treated with a mock treatment or Sal2. Kinetic parameters of PDC, fumarase, and MDH were additionally measured as described above. Both PDC and fumarase activity could be modified by incubation with PP2c63 or PP2c63 plus Sal2, but not with Sal2 alone (Figure 2B and 2D, Supplemental Figures 9B and 10B). The activity of MDH was unaltered by incubation with either PP2c63 or Sal2 (Supplemental Figure 10).

Metabolite profiling of the mutants and WT

To further analyze regulation of the TCA cycle, we performed metabolite profiling of WT plants and all mutant lines at four time points (MD: middle of day, ED: end of day, MN: middle of night, and EN: end of the night) using 30-day-old plants. We were able to identify 56 primary metabolites using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis (Figure 3 and Supplemental Figure 12). Here, we focused on metabolites that were related to the observed alterations in phosphopeptide abundance and enzyme activity. Due to limitations of the GC-MS protocol employed, pyruvate could not be accurately quantified; however, the content of alanine, a product of pyruvate metabolism, was significantly decreased in all PDK-deficient mutant lines at the MD, ED, and MN. Consistent

Figure 2. Enzyme activity of mitochondrial PDC in purified mitochondria.

(A) Enzyme activities were measured in extracts from purified mitochondria with different concentrations of substrates.

(C) The K_m and the V_{max} of PDC were determined from a Michaelis-Menten equation with different substrate concentrations.

(B) Recombinant protein-based complementation of enzyme activity in purified mitochondria. Purified mitochondria from *pp2c63* were treated with recombinant SAL2, PP2c63, SAL2+PP2c63, or a mock solution for 30 min.

(D) The K_m and V_{max} of recombinant protein- complemented PDC were determined from a Michaelis-Menten equation with different substrate concentrations. Data presented are mean \pm SD ($n = 4$). Black points (A and B) and bold values (C and D) indicate values significantly different from the WT by the Student's t test at 5% ($*P < 0.05$).

with the lower K_m of PDC observed, alanine content was significantly higher in *sal2 pp2c63* lines at the MD and decreased at the ED (Figure 3, Supplemental Figure 11A and 11C). Low levels of alanine provide further evidence that loss of PDK increases PDC activity (Figure 2A). Since the TCA cycle does not operate as a cycle in the light (Sweetlove et al., 2010), the ED and MN time points likely provide more information about TCA cycle flux. Hence, fumarate content was significantly increased at the ED, MD, and MN in *pp2c63*, consistent with the higher enzyme kinetic parameters of fumarase (Supplemental Figure 11). The malate content was significantly increased at the MN and the EN in all *sal2* and *pp2c63* lines, which is supported by increased MDH enzyme activity (Supplemental Figure 10A and Supplemental Table 2). Changes in other metabolites are discussed in the supplementary material.

Isotope redistribution in TCA cycle intermediates and their associated pathways

Investigation of flux is important because changes in metabolic fluxes can occur without changes in the metabolite pool size of pathway intermediates and *vice versa*, making it easy to underestimate or even miss important mechanisms of metabolic regulation based on information about steady-state metabolite levels alone. Use of stable isotopes allows for quantitative evaluation

of carbon flow in a broad range of metabolic pathways without the need for laborious (and potentially inaccurate) chemical fractionation procedures commonly used in the estimation of fluxes following incubation with radiolabeled substrates. To obtain better insight into the role of mitochondrial PDK, Sal2, and PP2c63 in the regulation of the TCA cycle *in vivo*, we therefore performed feeding experiments using ^{13}C -glucose and ^{13}C -pyruvate for a period of 4 h as in our previous paper (Daloso et al., 2015). For these experiments, leaves were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and metabolites were extracted, derivatized, and evaluated by a specially modified GC-MS protocol.

Following [^{13}C]-glucose feeding, significantly altered label accumulation in heavy isotope peaks (i.e., enhanced heavy isotope labeling with respect to the control treatment of the same genotype with unlabeled glucose) was observed in six metabolites (Figure 4A and Supplemental Figure 14). This included decreased labeling in fumarate in all mutant lines. In the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant, aspartate labeling was reduced, while citrate and succinate labeling were enhanced. Following ^{13}C -pyruvate feeding, citrate labeling increased in the *pdk* single mutant (Figure 4B), as expected from the increased PDC activity. The *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant also showed reduced labeling of aspartate, fumarate, and succinate, indicating that TCA cycle flux was altered.

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Figure 3. The TCA cycle-related metabolites in WT, sal2, pp2c63, pdk, and sal2 pp2c63.

Selected metabolites were quantified at four time points: MD, middle of the day; ED, end of the day; MN, middle of the night; EN, end of the night. Data are mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$ plants). The color scale indicates log₂-fold differences between WT and mutants. Asterisks indicate significant differences between WT and mutants determined by the Student's *t*-test at 5% ($P < 0.05$).

Protein-protein interactions between TCA cycle enzymes and mitochondrial phosphatases or the PDK kinase

The two mitochondrial phosphatases and PDK were transformed into the PSB-D Arabidopsis plant cell culture, which was used to detect mitochondria protein-protein interactions in previous research (Zhang et al., 2017, 2018). A GFP-tag-based modified AP-MS procedure was implemented using at least three biological replicates (Figure 5A–5C). In the subsequent data analysis, normalized signal intensities were processed to determine the fold change in abundance (FC-A) compared with mitochondrially expressed GFP using the SAINT algorithm embedded within CRAPome software (Choi et al., 2012; Morris et al., 2014). We considered only TCA cycle enzymes for which the intensity score was in the top 5%, which corresponded to an FC-A value of at least four, as positive interactions (Supplemental Table 3). PDK was found to interact with PDC1a-1/1a-2 and ACO2/3, and these interactions were confirmed by BiFC (Figures 5A, 5D and Supplemental Figure 15). Given the transient interaction of phosphatases, the interaction between PP2c63 and PDC1a-1 displayed a very large SD; however, this interaction was also confirmed by BiFC (Figure 5B and 5E). In addition, Sal2 and PP2c63 were shown by both AP-MS and BiFC to interact with mMDH1 and ACO3 (Figures 5B, 5C, 5F, and 5G and Supplemental Figure 15). Phosphatase and kinase targets fused with mCitrine and PDC1a-1/mMDH1/ACO3 fused with mCherry were also co-expressed in *Nicotiana tabacum* leaves (Supplemental Figure 16A–16E). As such interactions could only be transiently

observed, a split luciferase assay in Arabidopsis mesophyll protoplasts was also performed. Only the interaction between PP2c1a-1 and PP2c63 could be confirmed using this assay (Supplemental Figure 16F). These results are consistent with the regulation of phosphopeptide abundance by Sal2 and PP2c63, but due to the known complexity in determining interaction partners for phosphatases and kinases, such results do not exclude the other regulatory interactions described above.

DISCUSSION

While proteomic approaches have identified myriad putative targets of phosphorylation in plant cells (Zulawski et al., 2012), including those in plant mitochondria (Møller, 2016; Rao et al., 2017), metabolic and physiological studies of the impact of phosphorylation on TCA cycle enzymes have been restricted to the PDC to date (Møller et al., 2020). Here we used a combination of proteomic, metabolomic, and flux profiling approaches alongside enzyme activity measurements, *in vitro* enzyme dephosphorylation, and protein-protein interaction studies to evaluate the physiological roles of two phosphatases, Sal2 and PP2c63, that are weakly associated with TCA cycle enzymes (Zhang et al., 2017, 2018), in addition to the relatively well characterized PDK (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003). Our results suggest that PDK specifically catalyzes pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphorylation and that PP2c63 plays a direct role in regulating *in vivo* activities of PDC via dephosphorylation (Figure 6). This in turn, regulates flux through the TCA cycle, which is critical for both energy supply and the provision of the metabolic building blocks to sustain plant growth (Lan et al., 2012; Ohbayashi et al., 2019). The data we present suggest that Sal2 and PP2c63 exhibit slightly overlapping activities (as Sal2 indirectly regulates PDC) and reveal that a lack of both phosphatases results in a reduced number of leaves per plant and a reduction of growth overall.

At first, this result was surprising, as such a dramatic phenotype has not been previously observed in a battery of mutant Arabidopsis and tomato lines deficient in the expression of individual TCA cycle enzymes (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2013). Indeed, deficiency in aconitase (Carrari et al., 2003), mitochondrial MDH (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2005), and succinate dehydrogenase (Araújo et al., 2011a) result in enhanced growth (and yield in the case of tomato); however, the majority of the other TCA cycle mutants do not result in a growth penalty (the exception is *mmdh1/2*). Deficiency of mitochondrial fumarase in tomato results in moderately reduced growth (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2007), while overexpression of the mitochondrial dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase, a subunit shared by the PDC, 2-oxoglutarate dehydrogenase, branched-chain 2-oxoacid dehydrogenase complex, and glycine decarboxylase complex results in enhanced growth of Arabidopsis (Timm et al., 2015).

The severe phenotypes of the phosphatase mutants here may be explained by such phosphatases acting on more than one TCA cycle enzyme, with partial redundancy potentially explaining why these phenotypes only become apparent when both Sal2 and PP2c63 are absent. As plant photosynthetic carbon assimilation can be altered by modulating the TCA cycle (Nunes-Nesi et al., 2011), the growth phenotype of the double mutant is not surprising, and the even stronger growth phenotype when Sal2,

Figure 4. Redistributive ¹³C label enrichment in selected metabolites following incubation of leaves from WT, sal2, pp2c63, pdk, and sal2 pp2c63

(A and B) Fully expanded leaves of 30-day-old plants were detached in the middle of the light period and fed via the petiole with 15 mM [U-¹³C]-glucose (A) or [U-¹³C]-pyruvate (B) solution. Data presented are mean ± SEM (n = 5 plant replicates).

(C) All the data presented in a heatmap. Asterisks indicate values significantly different from WT by the Student's t test at 5% (*P < 0.05).

PP2c63, and PDK are absent may reflect additive effects of even stronger mis-regulation of PDC in a background where other TCA cycle enzymes are already mis-regulated. It is important to note that while plants lacking PP2c63 showed reduced fumarase activation, sal2 and pp2c63 mutants would be expected to have differing effects compared to knockouts of these genes. Intriguingly, the plant growth phenotype observed in the double mutant is the opposite of that following downregulation of MDH expression but not of fumarase expression. In addition, both the activity and kinetics of PDC and fumarase were significantly altered, which may have resulted in reduced plant growth and the dramatic metabolic changes observed in this genotype (Figure 2 and Supplemental Figures 9 and 11). It is also possible that other enzymes were affected, but that the corresponding phosphosites were not accessible by mass spectrometry. Consistent with this suggestion, we observed

changes in the overall activities of several other TCA cycle enzymes without alterations in phosphosites in both single and double mutants. Perhaps surprisingly, under our growth conditions, deficiency in PDK resulted in neither differences in leaf number nor growth, despite such phenotypes being previously reported (Tovar-Méndez et al., 2003).

In general, the results of the phosphoproteomics, enzyme activity, and protein interaction studies produced highly complementary results. Here phosphopeptides identified in the mitochondrial TCA cycle were very similar to those previously reported (Havelund et al., 2013; Møller, 2016). In light of these earlier studies (Havelund et al., 2013), we were unable to detect phosphopeptides for any of the mitochondrial isocitrate dehydrogenases. Both pp2c63 and sal2 pp2c63 double mutant, but not the sal2 pp2c63 pdk triple mutant or indeed any other of the mutants studied here, displayed a difference in isocitrate dehydrogenase activity either under substrate-saturated or -limited conditions (Supplemental Table 2). These data rule out an effect of PP2c63 on isocitrate dehydrogenase, but are not sufficient to do the same for the combined activities of Sal2 and PP2c63, or even Sal2 working in isolation. This suggests further focused experimentation on these enzymes is required in the future.

Given that pyruvate was not well characterized in our GC-MS measurements, alanine, which is partly synthesized from pyruvate, was taken as a proxy. Alanine levels were significantly higher in the sal2 pp2c63 double mutant and lower in pdk. As malate content is dependent on both the TCA cycle and photosynthesis, the malate level was not significantly altered at either the MD or at the ED. In addition, and in agreement with the anticipated altered flux through the TCA cycle, succinate content was also significantly altered in all mutant lines at the MD and at the EN. Changes in metabolites were observed following feeding with ¹³C-glucose or ¹³C-pyruvate. Given that the sal2 pp2c63 mutant displayed decreased pyruvate dehydrogenase activity, it is likely that labeled glucose was redistributed to the TCA cycle via malate. This resulted in high label redistribution to citrate and succinate via concerted increases in fumarase and MDH activities. In addition, when feeding ¹³C-pyruvate, pdk lines accumulated more labeled citrate, while in the sal2 pp2c63 lines the amounts of label in aspartate, fumarate, and succinate were significantly reduced. These metabolic responses are highly consistent with changes in flux of the TCA cycle that would be expected from our protein interaction and enzymology results.

When looking at the roles of other members of the Arabidopsis Sal family, Sal1, Sal2, and Sal4 all interact with one another and with PINIOD kinase to direct auxin transport polarity and plant development by directly regulating auxin efflux proteins (Lillo et al., 2014). Sal1 also participates in plant immunity (Ishiga et al., 2017). Sal2 is distinctive in that it harbors a unique C-terminal domain and localizes to mitochondria. Sal2 was also related to proline accumulation in a recent genome-wide association study (Verslues et al., 2014). Beyond plants, the yeast SAP185 (which is a protein homolog of Sal2) interacts with IDH and PDK (Breitkreutz et al., 2010), although the function of SAP185 remains to be elucidated. Looking at the Arabidopsis PP2C family, these protein phosphatases

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Figure 5. Protein-protein interactions between Sal2, PP2c63, PDK, and TCA cycle enzymes.

Affinity purification of PDK (A), PP2c63 (B), Sal2 (C), and mitochondrial signal peptide with C-terminal GFP was performed in plant cell culture. Following affinity purification using a GFP-binding protein, the protein complexes were digested by trypsin, followed by label-free LC-MS/MS quantification. The fold changes presented were normalized to the values obtained for mitochondrial GFP lines. Proteins were considered to be interactors when the intensity was in the top 5%, which corresponds to a fold-change value of at least 4. Data presented are mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Asterisks indicate significant enrichment of the peptides as determined by a Student's t test at 5% ($P < 0.05$). (D-G) The four positive protein interactions were tested by BiFC with transient expression of tagged proteins in Arabidopsis mesophyll cells. Images from left to right show the BiFC signal, autofluorescence, bright-field images, and merged images. (D) PDK-SCYCE/PDC1a-1-VYNE; (E) PP2c63-SCYCE/PDC1a-1-VYNE; (F) PP2c63-SCYCE/mMDH1-VYNE; (G) Sal2-SCYCE/mMDH1-VYNE; (H) Aco3-SCYCE/PDC1a-1-VYNE. (H) shows a representative negative control.

separate into 10 multi-protein clades with the addition of six singletons and are mostly localized to the cytosol (Schweighofer et al., 2004). Clade D PP2C proteins (PP2C.D) are the exception to this, with PP2c63 being localized to mitochondria (Tovar-Mendez et al., 2014). While the function of PP2c63 was previously unknown, its protein sequence is highly similar to the yeast protein PTC5, which is suggested to act as an unspecific pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase that is regulated in response to different metabolic states (Guo et al., 2017). In addition, PP2C.D phosphatases are also suggested to interact with SAUR proteins (Ren et al., 2018), and the phosphorylation status of both SAUR78 and SAUR9 were altered in our phosphoproteomic analysis. This finding suggests that PP2c63 may also indirectly regulate SAURs in the cytosol, which are key effector outputs of hormonal and environmental signals that regulate plant growth and development (Ren and Gray, 2015). This hypothesis would prove an exciting area for future research.

In summary, the results presented here greatly broaden our knowledge of plant TCA cycle regulation via phosphorylation. The results presented here confirm previous assumptions that PDK is a specific kinase but also suggest that dephosphorylation of phosphorylated PDC is directly catalyzed by PP2c63 (Figure 6). This was demonstrated at several levels, both in cellular extracts and with isolated mitochondria from mutant lines and following protein complementation assays. Moreover, for some of these modifications, we were able to identify likely regulatory phosphosites. However, further research, using phosphomimetic mutants to elucidate if these sites are truly regulatory and whether further sites are also involved, will be required. Our results also suggest that Sal2 may indirectly regulate the TCA cycle. Thus, PP2c63 and Sal2 phosphatases may operate in tandem as part of a complicated regulatory network, which also includes thioredoxin regulation (Daloso et al., 2015) and methionine sulfoxidation (Rao et al., 2015), to ensure that flux through the various reactions of the TCA cycle

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Figure 6. Schematic overview of phosphorylation of TCA cycle proteins

Proteins are shown as spheres. Metabolites are shown as black text. Changes in protein phosphorylation status and enzyme kinetics are shown in the box (original data are shown in Table 1 and Figure 2). Protein interactions are shown as black arrows between proteins. A change in activity or kinetics after incubation *in vitro* with phosphatases (“*in vitro* dephosphorylation”) is indicated by green coloring; original data are shown in Figure 3). A red circle around an enzyme indicates a change in absolute enzyme activity in the *sal2 pp2c63* double mutant (original data are shown in Supplemental Table 2). Abbreviations: PDC, pyruvate dehydrogenase complex; ME, malic enzyme; CSY, citrate synthase; ACO, aconitase; IDH, isocitrate dehydrogenase; ODC, oxoglutarate dehydrogenase complex; SLS, succinyl-CoA synthetase; SDH, succinate dehydrogenase; FUM, fumarase; MDH, malate dehydrogenase; Ac-CoA, acetyl-CoA; 2OG, 2-oxoglutarate; Suc-CoA, succinyl-CoA.

is maintained at an appropriate level depending on the cellular circumstances (Möller et al., 2020). Disruption of this network results in changes in metabolite levels and TCA cycle flux and severe inhibition of growth. In addition to addressing a crucial biological question, these data also demonstrate the power of combining broad profiling approaches with classical biochemistry in the investigation of metabolic regulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant growth conditions

Arabidopsis thaliana genotype Columbia (Col-0) (WT) and the T-DNA insertion mutants *pp2c63* (AT4g33920, SALK_143298 and GABI_494G12), *sal2* (AT1g30470, SAIL_142_C10 and SALK_122002), *pdk* (AT3G06483, SALK_018663 and SALK_014790), *sal2 pp2c63* (SAIL_142_C10/SALK_143298), *sal2 pdk* (SAIL_142_C10/SALK_018663), *pp2c63 pdk* (SALK_143298/SALK_018663), and *sal2 pp2c63 PDK* (SAIL_142_C10/SALK_143298/SALK_018663) were used in this study. Seeds were plated on Murashige and Skoog medium supplemented with 1% (w/v) sucrose for 10 days. Seedlings were then transferred to soil and grown under 8 h light (22°C)/16 h dark (18°C) growth conditions

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at a light intensity of 120–150 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Pre-bolting mature rosette leaves of 30-day-old Arabidopsis plants were harvested for metabolite measurement, phosphoproteomics, enzyme activity, lipidomics, and ^{13}C labeling experiments. *sal2* and *pp2c63* lines were complemented by full-length genomic DNA in PMDC110. Due to the weak growth phenotype of the double mutant, this line proved to be difficult to transform, so only one line transformed with the native PP2c63 gene linked with a C-terminal GFP fusion was selected.

cDNA cloning and vector construction

Full-length coding sequences of the genes encoding mitochondrially localized Arabidopsis phosphatases, kinase, aconitase, and PDC were cloned from a cDNA library generated from 2-week-old plants by PCR-based Gateway BP cloning using the pDONR207 Donor vector (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA). Gene-specific primers did not include the stop codon to ensure C-terminal fusion of tags (Supplemental Table 4). Expression vectors for AP-MS, BiFC, and complementation were constructed using the Gateway LR reaction with pK7FWG2, PMDC110, and binary BiFC-GATEWAY-Destination vectors and split-luciferase vectors (Zhang et al., 2017), respectively (Supplemental Table 4). The mCitrine and mCherry sequences were sub-cloned with the related genes into pdonor207 and pdonor L4-L3 by the In-Fusion (Clontech) method, and then sub-cloned into pK7m34GW2-8m21GW3 (VIB) by means of the LR reaction (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for co-sublocalization assays (Zhang et al., 2020b).

Chlorophyll-a fluorescence measurements and leaf absorbance

An F-6500 fluorometer (Jasco Inc., Groß-Umstadt, Germany) was used to measure 77 K chlorophyll-a fluorescence emission spectra from freshly isolated thylakoid membranes equivalent to 10 μg chlorophyll mL^{-1} . The sample was excited at 430 nm with a bandwidth of 10 nm, and the emission spectrum was recorded between 655 and 800 nm in 0.5-nm intervals with a bandwidth of 1 nm. *In vivo* measurements of chlorophyll-fluorescence parameters at 22°C were performed using a Dual-PAM instrument (Heinz Walz GmbH). Light-response curves of linear electron flux, non-photochemical quenching (qN), and the redox state of the PSII acceptor side (qL) were measured after 30 min of dark adaptation. Light intensity was increased stepwise from 0 to 2500 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, with a measuring time of 150 s for each light intensity under light-limited conditions and 60 s under light-saturated conditions. Linear electron transport was corrected for leaf absorbance, which was calculated from leaf transmittance and reflectance spectra as 100% minus transmittance (%) minus reflectance (%). Spectra were measured between 400 and 700 nm using an integrating sphere attached to a photometer (V650, Jasco Inc.). The spectral bandwidth was set to 1 nm, and the scanning rate was 200 nm min^{-1} (Schöttler et al., 2017).

Sample preparation for proteomics

Proteins were extracted from lyophilized leaf tissue using an adapted filter aided sample preparation protocol and processed by trypsin digestion (Lassowskat et al., 2017). For total proteome quantification, 10 μg of each peptide sample was fractionated into three fractions using SDB-RPS tips (Lassowskat et al., 2017). For phosphopeptide enrichment, 500 μg of peptides were enriched on titanium dioxide (TiO_2) beads as described previously (Nakagami, 2014). Eluted phosphopeptides were also fractionated on SDB-RPS tips.

LC-MS/MS data acquisition and data analysis

Dried peptides were re-dissolved in 2% (v/v) acetonitrile, 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid and adjusted to a final concentration of 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$. Samples were analyzed on an EASY-nLC 1200 coupled to a Q-Exactive HF mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Peptides (5 μL) were separated on in-house packed 18 cm frit-less silica emitters (New Objective, 0.75 μm inner diameter) containing reversed-phase ReproSil-Pur C18 AQ 1.9 μm resin (Dr. Maisch) and eluted using a 115-min segmented linear

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gradient with 300 nL/min from 5% to 98% buffer B (buffer A, 0.1% [v/v] formic acid, buffer B, 80% [v/v] acetonitrile, and 0.1% [v/v] formic acid). Mass spectra were acquired in data-dependent acquisition mode with a TOP12 method. MS spectra were acquired in the Orbitrap analyzer with a mass range of 300 to 1,759 m/z at a resolution of 120,000 FWHM and a target value of 3×10^6 ions. Precursors were selected with an isolation window of 1.2 m/z. HCD fragmentation was performed at a normalized collision energy of 25. MS/MS spectra were acquired with a target value of 5×10^4 ions at a resolution of 15,000 FWHM, a maximum injection time (max.) of 150 ms, and a fixed first mass of m/z 100. Peptides with a charge of +1, greater than 6, or with unassigned charge state were excluded from fragmentation for MS²; dynamic exclusion for 30 seconds prevented repeated selection of precursors.

Raw data were analyzed using the MaxQuant software (version 1.6.12.0) (Tyanova et al., 2016a) and searched against the Araport11 database (www.araport.org), including a contaminants list containing 246 contaminant proteins and a decoy database (Cheng et al., 2017). Trypsin was set as the protease and a maximum of two missed cleavages were allowed. Input and TiO₂-enriched samples were analyzed in different parameter groups. Phosphorylation of serine, threonine, and tyrosine was only searched in the group containing the TiO₂-enriched samples. For quantification, the label-free quantitation (LFQ) algorithm including separate LFQ for parameter groups was enabled. In addition, match between runs was used. The false discovery rate (FDR) cutoff for PSMs and proteins was set to 1%, the minimum score for modified peptides was set to 40, and the minimum delta score was set to 6.

Statistical analysis was performed using the Perseus software package (version 1.6.5.0) with a two-tailed *t* test with a permutation-based FDR of 0.05 (Tyanova et al., 2016b). LFQ intensities for protein groups and phosphopeptide intensities were log₂-transformed and reverse hits and potential contaminants were removed before the data analysis. The data were filtered for three valid values in at least one group. Missing values in the datasets for each mutant line were pairwise imputed against WT using R (version 3.6.1) with the impute package (version 1.60.0). Two to four missing values within one group were imputed using the minimal intensity for each experiment. For normalization, replicates were centered by subtracting the difference of a linear regression over replicates and the median of each experiment, followed by quantile normalization of the experiments with the preprocess Core package (version 1.48.0) for R. Statistical testing of the resulting dataset was performed with a two-tailed Student's *t* test (FDR 0.05), and volcano plots were plotted using the ggplot2 package (version 3.3.0). Average phosphorylation occupancies were calculated based on the MaxQuant occupancy data given in the phosphosite output table. Mass spectrometry proteomics data are deposited in the ProteomeXchange Consortium (<http://proteomecentral.proteomeexchange.org>) via the JPOST repository (Deutsch et al., 2016) with the data set identifier PXD018412.

Parallel reaction monitoring

Parallel reaction monitoring experiments were set up on the QExactive HF in PRM mode. TiO₂-enriched phosphopeptides (5 μL) were separated on in-house packed 18 cm frit-less silica emitters (New Objective, 0.75 μm inner diameter) containing reversed-phase ReproSil-Pur C18 AQ 1.9 μm resin (Dr. Maisch) and eluted using a 78-min segmented linear gradient with 300 nL/min from 5% to 98% buffer B (buffer A, 0.1% [v/v] formic acid, buffer B, 80% [v/v] acetonitrile and 0.1% [v/v] formic acid). Mass spectra were acquired in PRM mode for selected precursor ions with an isolation window of 1.0 m/z. MS² spectra were acquired in the Orbitrap analyzer at a resolution of 15 000 FWHM and a target value of 1×10^6 ions and a maximum injection time of 65 ms. HCD fragmentation was performed at a normalized collision energy of 25. Peak areas of transitions of the phosphorylated S292/S296 PDH E1 precursor ion (837.82202²⁺) were analyzed and quantified using Skyline (MacLean et al., 2010).

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Mitochondrial isolation and enzyme activity assays

Mitochondria were isolated from 10-day old Arabidopsis liquid shaking cultures grown under short-day photoperiod conditions as described by Kerbler and Taylor (2017). Briefly, ~30 g of whole seedlings was disrupted in a precooled mortar and pestle using 150 mL of cold extraction buffer (0.3 M sucrose, 25 mM tetrasodiumpyrophosphate [10 H₂O], 2 mM EDTA, 10 mM KH₂PO₄, 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone [PVP-40], 1% BSA, 20 mM ascorbic acid, 5 mM cysteine [pH 7.5]). The homogenate was filtered twice through four layers of Miracloth (CalBioChem). The material that was retained was recovered and re-ground with 100 mL extraction buffer. This step was repeated three times. The filtrate was first centrifuged at 2,500g for 5 min to separate the chloroplast (pellet) and mitochondrial (supernatant) fractions. The supernatant containing the mitochondria-enriched fraction was further centrifuged for 15 min at 18,000g. The pellet was resuspended in a small volume of washing buffer (0.3 M sucrose, 10 mM TES-KOH, and 0.1% [w/v] BSA [pH 7.5]). An additional 35 mL of washing buffer was added, and the mixture was centrifuged again at 2,500g for 5 min. The supernatant was transferred to new tubes (40 mL), making sure that no pellet was also carried over. The suspension was then centrifuged at 18,000g for 15 min. The obtained pellet was resuspended in 2 mL of washing buffer and loaded on top of a 28% (v/v) Percoll (GE Healthcare) continuous gradient with a 0% to 4% (w/v) PVP-40 linear gradient and centrifuged at 38,000g for 50 min. The mitochondrial band was collected, washed three times in sucrose wash buffer (without BSA) (0.3 M sucrose, 10 mM TES-KOH [pH 7.5]) and divided into aliquots for measuring enzyme activity.

Purified mitochondria were lysed in the extraction buffer (extraction buffer: 8.7% [v/v] glycerol, 0.5% [w/v] BSA, 1% [v/v] Triton X-100, 50 mM 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid (HEPES)/KOH pH 7.5, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA), 1 mM ethylene glycol tetraacetic acid (EGTA), 1 mM benzamidine, 1 mM ε-aminocaproic acid, 10 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF) in isopropanol, 0.2 mM leupeptin, and 50 mM dithiothreitol) for mitochondrial enzyme activity measurement (Omena-Garcia et al., 2017).

Total protein extracted from purified mitochondria or total leaf extractions were used to analyze citrate synthase, NAD-IDH, NADP-IDH, fumarase, NAD-MDH, aconitase, SDH, SCoAL, and PDC as described previously (Daloso et al., 2015; Omena-Garcia et al., 2017). For enzyme kinetic assays using purified mitochondrial samples, a series of pyruvate concentrations (1, 2.5, 5, 7.5, and 10 mM) were added to 20 μg of broken isolated mitochondria to perform the PDC assay (Omena-Garcia et al., 2017). Similarly, a series of fumarate concentrations (2.5, 5, 12.5, 25, and 50 mM) were added to 20 ng of broken isolated mitochondria to perform the fumarase assay. For total protein extractions, plants were grown under short-day conditions for 30 days to determine diurnal enzyme kinetics changes. Activity was expressed by FW or by protein content determined using a Bradford's assay (Bio-rad).

In vitro enzyme assays were performed using the standard protein dephosphorylation assay. Total mitochondrial protein (100 μg) was dephosphorylated with 0.1 μg of recombinant PP2c63 or Sal2 in NEBuffer MetalloPhosphatases buffer (50 mM HEPES [pH 7.5], 0.1% 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl) dimethylammonio] propanesulfonate, 100 mM NaCl, 1 mM MnCl₂) for 30 min at 30°C.

Affinity purification mass spectrometry

Affinity purification mass spectrometry (AP-MS) was conducted by expressing target proteins fused with a C-terminal GFP tag in the PSB-D Arabidopsis cell culture line using a published protocol (Van Leene et al., 2011). Tandem GFP fused with an N-terminal mitochondrial targeting peptide was used as a negative control. PSB-D cells (Arabidopsis Biological Resource Center) were cultured in the dark at 25°C with shaking at 120 rpm. The cell line was cultured on Murashige and

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Skoog Basal Salts with minimal organics medium (MSMO; Sigma-Aldrich, Gillingham, UK) supplemented with 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$ kinetin, 0.5 mg/L 1-naphthaleneacetic acid, and 3% sucrose (Zhang et al., 2019).

Cells were sub-cultured every week at a 1 to 10 (v/v) culture to fresh media ratio. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain GV3101 pMP90 transformed with an expression vector was grown on a plate for 2 days and then resuspended into MSMO medium to an OD600 of 1.0. A 3 mL aliquot of a 2-day-old PSB-D cell culture was mixed with 200 μL of *A. tumefaciens* suspension and 6 μL of 100 mM acetosyringone and co-cultivated for 72 h. Transformed cells were selected in medium containing 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ kanamycin, 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$ carbenicillin, and 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$ vancomycin for three rounds of 1-week subculture followed by two rounds of subculture in medium containing only kanamycin (Van Leene et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2019). Expression and localization of the tagged proteins were evaluated by viewing GFP fluorescence using confocal microscopy. The transformed cells were collected by vacuum filtration at 5 days after subculturing and frozen in liquid nitrogen. After grinding into a fine powder using a ball mill (MM301; Retch, Haan, Germany), proteins were extracted by mixing 2 g of material with 2 mL extraction buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 15 mM MgCl_2 , 5 mM EGTA, 1 mM dithiothreitol, and 1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride). Following removal of cell debris by repeated centrifugation at 22,000g, 4°C for 5 min, the supernatant was mixed with 25 μL of GFP-Trap_A slurry (ChromoTek, Martinsried, Germany) equilibrated with extraction buffer and incubated for 1 h at 4°C with rotation. The beads were collected by centrifugation at 3,000g, 4°C for 3 min and washed three times each with extraction buffer containing 0, 250, and 500 mM NaCl.

The proteins remaining on the beads were subsequently subjected to in-solution digestion by LysC and trypsin and the resulting peptides were purified (Wiśniewski et al., 2009). LC-MS/MS analysis was performed on a Q Exactive Plus (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Quantitative analysis of MS/MS measurements was performed with the Progenesis IQ software (Nonlinear Dynamics, Newcastle, UK). Proteins were identified from spectra using Mascot (Matrix Science, London, UK). Mascot search parameters were set as follows: TAIR10 protein annotation, requirement for tryptic ends, one missed cleavage allowed, fixed modification: carbamidomethylation (cysteine), variable modification: oxidation (methionine), peptide mass tolerance = ± 10 ppm, MS/MS tolerance = ± 0.6 Da, allowed peptide charges of +2 and +3. A decoy database search was used to limit FDRs to 1% at the protein level. Peptide identifications below rank one or with a Mascot ion score below 25 were excluded. Mascot results were imported into Progenesis Q1, quantitative peak area information extracted, and the results exported for data plotting and statistical analysis. These intensities were filtered against experiment control and normalized using the spectral index (SIN) in the CRAPome website (Mellacheruvu et al., 2013). Finally, the possible interactions were scored as fold change-A score (FC-A) calculated by the SAINT algorithm (Choi et al., 2012; Mellacheruvu et al., 2013) (Supplemental Table 3).

Affinity purification was performed in five experiments resulting in at least three independent biological replicates. Fold change (FC) values were calculated for each individual replicate. All FC-A scores of the detected peptides are presented in Supplemental Table 3. Finally, the interaction pairs with FC scores above 4 were selected and analyzed by SUBA4 (Hooper et al., 2017) in order to restrict defined interactors to those proteins that are colocalized to the mitochondria (Supplemental Table 3).

Bimolecular-fluorescent complementation

Bimolecular-fluorescent complementation (BiFC) constructs were expressed in Arabidopsis leaves. Briefly, transformed agrobacteria were washed with 10 mM MgCl_2 and 100 μM acetosyringone with an OD of approximately 12, and then diluted with infiltration buffer ($1/4$ Murashige

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and Skoog [pH 6.0], 1% sucrose, 100 μM acetosyringone, 0.005% [v/v, 50 $\mu\text{L/L}$] Silwet L-77). Agrobacteria (OD 0.5) were infiltrated into 2- to 3-week-old Arabidopsis leaves (Zhang et al., 2020a). Confocal images were taken using a DM6000B/SP5 confocal laser scanning microscope (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). BiFC fluorescence was imaged by excitation with a 488 nm laser, and emission fluorescence was captured by 500 to 520-nm band-pass emission filters.

Split-LUC complementation assay

The plasmids for split-LUC assays were extracted from bacterial cells by alkaline lysis and purified using a silicon dioxide (Sigma-Aldrich) slurry. Mesophyll protoplasts were generated from the leaves of *Arabidopsis* Col-0 by the Tape-*Arabidopsis* Sandwich method as previous research (Zhang et al., 2017). For luminescence detection, 10 μL of 60 μM ViviRen Live Cell substrate (Promega, Madison, WI) was added to each well of a 96-well plate (Kato and Jones, 2010). The plate was kept for 4 min at room temperature in the dark before measuring the luminescence using a CLARIOstar microplate reader (BMG LABTECH, Ortenberg, Germany) with 10-s integration periods at emission 470 \pm 80 nm.

Co-sublocalization

Constructs for co-sublocalization were transiently expressed in the *N. tabacum* leaves by agro-infiltration (Zhang et al., 2020c). Confocal images were taken using a DM6000B/SP8 confocal laser scanning microscope.

Metabolite measurement

Metabolite profiling of *Arabidopsis* leaves (30 days old under short-day conditions) was carried out by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (ChromaTOF software, Pegasus driver 1.61; LECO) as described previously (Lisec et al., 2006). The chromatograms and mass spectra were evaluated using TagFinder software (Luedemann et al., 2012). Metabolite identification was manually checked by the mass spectral and retention index collection of the Golm Metabolome Database (Kopka et al., 2004). Peak heights of the mass fragments were normalized on the basis of the fresh weight of the sample and the added amount of an internal standard (ribitol). Statistical differences between groups were analyzed by Student's t tests on the raw data. Results were determined to be statistically different at a probability level of $P < 0.05$. The levels of starch in the tubers were determined as described previously (Zhang et al., 2014).

Analysis of [^{13}C]-glucose- and [^{13}C]-pyruvate-labeled samples

Arabidopsis leaves (30 days old under short-day conditions) of similar size, but from different genotypes, were fed via the petiole with 15 mM [^{13}C]-Glucose or [^{13}C]-pyruvate (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories) by incubation in buffered solution (10 mM MES-KOH [pH 6.5]) for 4 h. At the end of the incubation, leaves were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. They were subsequently extracted in 100% methanol, the fractional enrichment of metabolite pools was determined as described previously (Szecowka et al., 2013; Daloso et al., 2015), and label redistribution was expressed according to the method by (Stuart-Guimarães et al., 2007).

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental information can be found online at *Molecular Plant Online*.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Y.Z. and A.R.F. designed the experiments. J.G. and I.F. performed the quantitative phosphoproteomic and proteomic analyses. Y.Z., L.P.S., and D.M.D. performed the ¹³C label experiment and analysis. Y.Z. and B.S. performed the protein-protein interaction. Y.Z., S.M.K., D.B.M., and J.A. performed the enzyme activity measurements. Y.Z. performed metabolite profiling. Y.Z. and A.R.F. wrote the manuscript. I.F., S.M.K., D.K.H., and M.S. revised the manuscript.

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